

Taking into consideration all other factors, evaluate the extent to which Bletchley Park contributed to victory in Europe, 1939-45. (2,199 words)

*"ULTRA was essential to victory in the battle of the Atlantic, the war in Africa and the landings in Sicily and Normandy."*¹

*"ULTRA, in my humble opinion, has been exaggerated in importance."*²

*"... [ULTRA] shortened the war by not less than two years and probably by four years."*³

Debate over the importance of the decryption of high-level Axis signals traffic, particularly the Enigma and Fish cyphers, at Bletchley Park (codenamed ULTRA) - began as soon as the secret was revealed in 1974 and continues today. The Battle of Britain, the North African campaign and the Battle of the Atlantic have all been particularly credited as depending on ULTRA⁴.

The air campaign in the summer of 1940 is the easiest to address: ULTRA provided useful confirmation of the German order of battle, but little more⁵. Indeed, Dowding was not even cleared for ULTRA until after the battle⁶: the key intelligence asset for the Battle of Britain was the listening posts of the "Y Service" monitoring the working chatter of the Luftwaffe's frontline⁷.

¹ Deutsch H, "The Influence of Ultra on World War II", *Parameters*, December 1978

² Frankland N, "Some Thoughts About and Experience Of Official Military History", *The Journal Of The Royal Air Force Historical Society* No. 17

³ Hinsley H, "The Influence of ULTRA in the Second World War", Security Group Seminar, 19 Oct 1993

⁴ Deutsch.

⁵ Bungay S, "The Most Dangerous Enemy", 2000 Aurum

⁶ Lewin R, "Ultra Goes to War", 1978 Grafton

⁷ Jones R V, "Most Secret War", 1978 Hamish Hamilton

Even before the revelation of ULTRA, historians such as Roskill⁸ and Taylor⁹ credited attacks on Axis shipping – particularly those based from Malta – as decisive in containing, then defeating, the *Deutsche Afrika Korps* (DAK), citing Rommel’s warning in May 1941 that “without Malta the Axis will end by losing control of North Africa”. Subsequently, Deutsch¹⁰ and Hinsley¹¹ credited Rommel’s defeat to the strangulation of his supply lines, particularly due to ULTRA decrypts identifying the ships, schedules and routes for British attack. Even a logistician of Thompson’s calibre¹² highlighted the importance of Malta as a base of operations, from which attacks were guided by ULTRA.

However, as early as 1952 the US Army’s analysis¹³ concluded that most of Rommel’s logistic problems were of distribution rather than supply; and a detailed study by van Creveld¹⁴ confirmed that Rommel received plentiful supplies throughout the campaign: but ammunition and (especially) fuel delivered to Tripoli and then Benghazi, could not be brought forward effectively, and every advance made his situation worse.

Even with his disproportionate allocation of critically scarce motor transport¹⁵, the long distances, made movement from port to fighting front increasingly difficult and wasteful.

It was over four hundred miles just from Tripoli to El Agheila: when “that lout of a Rommel”¹⁶ made his tactically successful advance to Sollum – in direct defiance of explicit

⁸ Roskill S W, “The War At Sea 1939-1945 Volume II: The Period of Balance”, 1956 HMSO

⁹ Taylor A J P, “A History Of World War Two”, 1974 Octopus Books

¹⁰ Deutsch H C, “The Historical Impact of Revealing the Ultra Secret,” *Parameters*, September 1977

¹¹ Hinsley F H, “British Intelligence in the Second World War”, volume 2, 1981, HMSO

¹² Thompson J, “The Lifeblood of War: Logistics in Armed Conflict”, 1991 Brassey’s

¹³ Toppe A, “Desert Warfare: German Experiences in World War II”, 1952, Historical Division US Army

¹⁴ Van Creveld M, “Supplying War: Logistics From Wallenstein To Patton”, 1979 Cambridge University

¹⁵ The three divisions of Rommel’s *Deutsche Afrika Korps* enjoyed as much motor transport as thirty divisions on the Eastern Front (Van Creveld)

¹⁶ Cavallero U, “Commando Supremo”, 1948 Cappelli Editore

orders¹⁷ - he created a difficult situation. His supply situation became intolerable simply because of the distances involved¹⁸.

Examining Italian shipping records, O'Hara and Cernuschi¹⁹ confirmed van Creveld's analysis: over the course of the campaign, eighty-four per cent of the supplies despatched across the Mediterranean arrived²⁰. It was a shortage of fuel oil, not losses to the British underway, which proved the greatest constraint on shipping²¹ and it was inability to transport the supplies that kept them from the front line. Despite Rommel's complaints in mid-1942 – claiming in June that his forces were living 'hand to mouth' – fully 91,000 tons, much more than he needed, had been unloaded in Tripoli... from which there was no way to transport them to Alamein. The North African campaign ultimately proved the old adage "Amateurs study tactics, professionals study logistics"²².

The Battle of the Atlantic – where Doenitz's U-boats tried to cut off Britain's sea trade – is perhaps the campaign where ULTRA is most claimed decisive. The U-boat historian Jürgen Rohwer²³ assessed it as decisive in preventing the defeat of Britain, and Keegan describes how Bletchley Park's exclusion from the U-boat's "Shark" cypher (using the new four-rotor M4 Enigma) from February to December 1942 had a "calamitous effect on

¹⁷ Deutsch. One failing of ULTRA was that the order to Rommel not to conduct offensive operations until ordered to, was successfully decrypted: it was not expected that he would cheerfully ignore it.

¹⁸ It is further from Tripoli to El Alamein than from Berlin to Moscow.

¹⁹ O'Hara V P and Cernuschi E, "The Other Ultra: Signal Intelligence and the Battle to Supply Rommel's Attack toward Suez", *Naval War College Review*, Vol. 66, No. 3, summer 2013

²⁰ Cavallo described Italian shipping losses as 'light' as late as October 1942.

²¹ The shortage of fuel meant fewer ships could sail, and those that did went to Tripoli rather than Benghazi or Tobruk to save fuel (even though that took them much closer to Malta)

²² Attributed to General Omar Bradley, US Army

²³ Howarth S and Law D (eds), "The Battle of the Atlantic 1939-1945: The 50th Anniversary International Naval Conference", 1994 Naval Institute Press

sinkings”²⁴. However, the truth is inevitably far more complex – Kennedy alludes to the multiple interactions involved²⁵, but even there falls into other myths²⁶.

Regarding Figures 1 and 2, it is apparent that a reason for the dramatic increase in sinking in 1942 is simply because more U-boats were available. An additional factor was the move of the U-boat force to the French Atlantic coast, shortening their transit times and allowing longer patrols (hence more time to find and sink targets), and the resolution of some serious problems with German torpedoes²⁷.

²⁴ Keegan J, “Intelligence in War”, 2003 Hutchinson

²⁵ Kennedy P, “History from the Middle: The Case of The Second World War”, *Journal of Military History*, Jan 2010 Vol.74 No.1

²⁶ Kennedy mentions the importance of the “Hedgehog” forward-throwing weapon, but in fact tactical and technical issues meant “Hedgehog” only became effective in early 1944 - by which time the crisis had passed.

²⁷ Terraine J, “Business in Great Waters”, 1989 Leo Cooper

Figure 1 -Effect of convoy on sinking rates²⁸

Figure 2 - U-boat sinking rates²⁹

Another dramatic contributor to the success of the U-boats in 1942 was, ironically, the US's entry into the war. The unconvoied, unescorted ships along the US east coast – whose

²⁸ Preston A, "Submarines Since 1919", 1974 BPC Publishing

²⁹ Preston.

towns at first refused to even black out their lights – were easy prey. Five U-boats sent to start Operation *Paukenschlag* (Drumbeat) sank 27 vessels totalling 200,000 tons in just two weeks in January 1942, and many more followed – driving up the sinking rate just as Bletchley were shut out of “Shark”³⁰. The US responded slowly and clumsily, initially rejecting British experience (so ULTRA would have availed little)³¹

Additionally, the German codebreakers had not been idle. The *B-dienst* (*Beobachtungsdienst*, ‘observation service’) broke into the British Naval Cypher No. 3 in December 1941³², and were reading it until June 1943. This gave Doenitz key information on convoy sailings and locations, which his U-boats made full use of.³³

Doenitz’s peak success was 146 ships sunk in each of May and June 1942, after which sinkings fell sharply despite “Shark” resisting Bletchley’s best efforts. Part of this was due to the US belatedly adopting convoy and also setting up an equivalent of the Submarine Tracking Room³⁴, sharing information with London: this common picture became a key part of the anti-submarine battle³⁵.

³⁰ A classic example of correlation not equalling causation.

³¹ Blair C, “Hitler’s U-Boat War, The Hunted 1942-1945”, 1998 Random House

³² Mallmann-Showell J, “German Naval Codebreakers.”, 2003 Naval Institute Press

³³ The sharp rise in sinkings correlates not only with “Shark” denying ULTRA, but with the *B-Dienst* breaking into Admiralty convoy codes.

³⁴ Captain Roger Winn’s ‘Submarine Tracking Room’ was what would today be called an “intelligence fusion centre” where all available information was collated to estimate and track the position of individual U-boats. The loss of access to Doenitz’s Enigma affected its operation, but it remained a vital asset.

³⁵ Hackmann W, “Seek and Strike: Sonar, anti-submarine warfare and the Royal Navy 1914-54”, 1984 HMSO

Other innovations were logistic, tactical and technical: often interrelated. More and better radar sets first denied night surface attack, then made aircraft more capable at finding and attacking submarines. Effective high-frequency direction finding equipment³⁶ allowed aircraft and ships to quickly detect and attack U-boats making contact reports, however impervious the encryption of their signal. And, crucially, air cover over convoys extended, both as longer-ranged aircraft flew from land, more bases were built on islands like Ascension and the Azores, and the first escort carriers³⁷ joined convoys.

By August 1942, Doenitz –confident in June that his boats were winning the tonnage war – wrote despairingly in his War Diary³⁸ that his operations were “critically constrained” by Allied airpower. By November 1942, forecasts of Allied shipbuilding indicated that the U-boats would have to sink a million tons a month merely to keep pace with construction, and 1.3 million tons a month to produce a decisive effect³⁹. For perspective, even during the glory days of Operation *Paukenschlag*, the U-boats had achieved only 400,000 tons a month⁴⁰.

³⁶ Nicknamed ‘Huff-duff’ from the abbreviation HF/DF – the concept was not new, but the capability to *quickly* and *accurately* DF a high-frequency signal from a ship or aircraft was a breakthrough.

³⁷ The true ‘escort carrier’ was a utilitarian warship, mass-produced for a number of roles, but for the Battle of the Atlantic the ‘Merchant Aircraft Carrier’ – a tanker or bulk carrier fitted with a basic flight deck –also proved valuable.

³⁸ BdU KTB war diary, U-boat command, unpublished papers referenced by Padfield

³⁹ Padfield

⁴⁰ In May 1942 Doenitz had estimated that 700,000 tons a month would be sufficient, even allowing for ‘inflated estimates’ of US production capacity (Padfield)

The battle of the Atlantic had been fought and largely won by the time that “Shark” was broken in late 1942⁴¹. The final, ferocious struggles as Doenitz threw massed numbers into the campaign to overwhelm the Allied defenders – such as the battle of Convoys HX 229/SC 122 in March 1943^{42,43} – were almost independent of ULTRA. So many U-boats were at sea, and their intelligence from the *B-Dienst* good enough, that they simply could not be avoided or routed around. However, they could be fought very effectively by the improving escort forces: only a month later, Convoy ONS5 fended off attacks by nearly sixty U-boats, sinking seven and crippling five⁴⁴, and Convoy SC130 sank three U-boats⁴⁵ without loss to itself. In May 1943, Doenitz conceded defeat and withdrew his boats from the North Atlantic.⁴⁶

More widely and generally, ULTRA supported Allied intelligence gathering and deception efforts. However, while it confirmed that the *Wehrmacht* expected the main invasion of France to fall in the Pas de Calais, it took a concerted effort – from the disinformation of “Garbo”, to the creation of Patton’s ‘First US Army Group’⁴⁷ – to create and sustain the deception, and ULTRA was only able to increase the confidence that it had succeeded⁴⁸.

⁴¹ See Figure 1 for the reduced sinkings, and Figure 2 for the rising loss rate of U-boats.

⁴² Middlebrook M, “Convoy”, 1976 Viking Press

⁴³ Keegan J, “The Price of Admiralty: The Evolution of Naval Warfare”, 1990 Penguin

⁴⁴ Gretton P, “Convoy Escort Commander”, 1971 Corgi

⁴⁵ One of them U-954, which included Peter Doenitz – the Admiral’s youngest son - among its crew.

⁴⁶ Blair

⁴⁷ Appointing Patton to command FUSAG was an excellent example of reinforcing a deception by confirming an enemy’s preconceptions.

⁴⁸ Rankin N, “Churchill’s Wizards: The British Genius for Deception 1914-1945”, 2009 Faber & Faber

ULTRA certainly contributed significantly to the Allied war effort, though it is hard to confirm any single decisive effect. Hinsley's bold claim it "*shortened the war by not less than two years and probably by four*" and Deutsch's assertion that it was "*essential to victory*" fall down simply because of the Allied policy of "Germany First"⁴⁹; a Germany still resisting in August 1945 would enjoy the first fruits of the Manhattan Project, and by the end of 1946 the US had produced sixteen weapons. Logistic analysis^{50,51,52} highlights how Germany was doomed by mid-1942 and the first atom bombs form a decisive endstop, but Bletchley Park reduced the cost and – perhaps most importantly - the perceived risks of that victory.

⁴⁹ Willmott H, "Empires in the Balance", 1982 Naval Institute Press

⁵⁰ Tooze A, "The Wages of Destruction: The Making and Breaking of the Nazi War Economy", 2006 Allen Lane

⁵¹ Ellis J, "Brute Force", 1990 Penguin

⁵² Overy R, "How the Allies Won", 2006 Pimlico

References

Books

- BdU KTB war diary, U-boat command, unpublished papers referenced by Padfield
- Blair C, "Hitler's U-Boat War: The Hunted 1942-1945", 1998 Random House
- Bungay S, "The Most Dangerous Enemy", 2000 Aurum
- Cavallero U, "Commando Supremo", 1948 Cappelli Editore
- Ellis J, "Brute Force", 1990 Penguin
- Gretton P, "Convoy Escort Commander", 1971 Corgi
- Hackmann W, "Seek and Strike: Sonar, anti-submarine warfare and the Royal Navy 1914-54", 1984 HMSO
- Hinsley F H, "British Intelligence in the Second World War", volume 2, 1981, HMSO
- Hinsley H, "The Influence of ULTRA in the Second World War", Security Group Seminar, 19 Oct 1993
- Howarth S and Law D (eds), "The Battle of the Atlantic 1939-1945: The 50th Anniversary International Naval Conference", 1994 Naval Institute Press
- Jones R V, "Most Secret War", 1978 Hamish Hamilton
- Keegan J, "Intelligence in War", 2003 Hutchinson
- Keegan J, "The Price of Admiralty: The Evolution of Naval Warfare", 1990 Penguin
- Lewin R, "Ultra Goes to War", 1978 Grafton
- Mallmann-Showell J, "German Naval Codebreakers". 2003 Naval Institute Press
- Middlebrook M, "Convoy", 1976 Viking Press
- Overy R, "How the Allies Won", 2006 Pimlico
- Preston A, "Submarines since 1919", 1974 BPC Publishing
- Rankin N, "Churchill's Wizards: The British Genius for Deception 1914-1945", 2009 Faber & Faber
- Roskill S W, "The War at Sea 1939-1945 Volume II: The Period of Balance", 1956 HMSO
- Taylor A J P, "A History of World War Two", 1974 Octopus Books
- Terraine J, "Business in Great Waters", 1989 Leo Cooper
- Thompson J, "The Lifeblood of War: Logistics in Armed Conflict", 1991 Brassey's
- Tooze A, "The Wages of Destruction: The Making and Breaking of the Nazi War Economy", 2006 Allen Lane
- Toppe A, "Desert Warfare: German Experiences in World War II", 1952 Historical Division, US Army
- Van Creveld M, "Supplying War: Logistics from Wallenstein to Patton", 1979 Cambridge University Press
- Willmott H, "Empires in the Balance", 1982 Naval Institute Press

Journal Articles

- Deutsch H, "The Historical Impact of Revealing the Ultra Secret," *Parameters*, October 1977
- Deutsch H, "The Influence of Ultra on World War II", *Parameters*, December 1978

Frankland N, "Some Thoughts About and Experience of Official Military History", *The Journal Of The Royal Air Force Historical Society*, No. 17

Kennedy P, "History from the Middle: The Case of the Second World War", *Journal of Military History*, January 2010

Norris R and Kristensen H, "Global nuclear weapons inventories, 1945–2010", *Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists*, July/August 2010

O'Hara V P and Cernuschi E, "The Other Ultra: Signal Intelligence and the Battle to Supply Rommel's Attack toward Suez", *Naval War College Review*, summer 2013